

Female Fantasies and Romantic Retellings of the Myth of Persephone: A Case Study in Greek Mythology-Based Fanfiction

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Abstract

Modern retellings of the Persephone myth often depict her as a willing partner to Hades rather than an abducted victim. This portrayal has gained popularity on platforms like TikTok and Archive of Our Own (AO3), where fan interactions consolidate Persephone as a central figure in contemporary fandom culture. However, these interpretations have also sparked debate, with critics arguing that erasing the elements of abduction and lack of consent risks romanticizing harmful power dynamics and misrepresenting the original myth's themes. Using the frameworks of Classical Reception and Gender Studies, this paper addresses these debates by demonstrating how romantic fan reinterpretations of the Persephone myth can achieve feminist aims. With AO3 as a case study, I combine quantitative analysis with qualitative readings of fanfiction to explore how fans reimagine Persephone's story. The findings reveal that fan works often create a female-centred, feminist fantasy where romance with Hades exists only in the absence of violence against women. Ultimately, I argue that these stories allow young women, as both consumers and producers ('prosumers') of fanfiction, to envision lives on their own terms and celebrate their desires, even in contexts where societal norms have yet to fully accommodate them.

Introduction

Modern retellings of the Persephone myth often depict her not as the abducted maiden, but as the loving partner of Hades, her former captor. This notion has gained significant popularity in recent years on platforms like TikTok and *Archive of Our*

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Own,¹ where millions of interactions, posts, and fanfictions consolidate Persephone as a central figure in fandom culture.² For these fans, the goddess' agency is a central concern, as is evidenced in the fact that most works depict her choosing to be with Hades and applauding their relationship's virtues. This interpretation clashes with the views of some other fans and academics who argue that erasing Persephone's kidnapping is not only inaccurate,³ but also risks promoting harmful ideas, as these stories romanticize a relationship predicated on abduction, rape, and a lack of consent.

Drawing on the concepts and methods of Classical Reception and Gender Studies, this paper complicates such critiques by showing that romantic readings of the Persephone myth (particularly those emerging from fan communities) can achieve feminist ends. Given Persephone's current popularity in fanfiction forums, I focus on examples from this format, more specifically the fanfiction platform *Archive of Our Own*, as illustrative of the broader phenomenon. Classical Reception, with its focus on the cultural factors shaping new interpretations,⁴ provides a framework for moving beyond debates over authenticity to discover how romantic retellings relate to contemporary trends in feminism and reflect the communities that create them. Within fandom, mythology functions as 'canon', 'in the fannish sense of a source text of a fan community', upon which fanfiction of Persephone is based.⁵ Although the online 'Persephone canon' extends beyond strictly mythological sources, this paper focuses exclusively on mythology-based fanfictions for reasons that will be explained later.

The structure of this paper is as follows. I begin by exploring the episode of the abduction, as presented in the classical sources. Then I turn to an analysis of how Persephone is reimagined in fan works. This analysis is divided into two parts. The first one offers a quantitative commentary of search parameters and results gathered from *Archive of Our Own*. To interpret these results, I use the application Voyant Tools, which measures word frequency in large corpora and identifies general themes and ideas within the selected dataset. The second shifts to a deeper qualitative analysis, involving close readings of a selection of representative fanfics about Persephone. The fourth section engages with the question of how feminism shapes the readings found in *Archive of Our Own*.

Ultimately, the different concepts and methods used throughout this paper reach the same conclusion regarding the reception of the Persephone myth in fanfiction. Most fans are driven by an urgent necessity to write about what they truly desire: a female and feminist fantasy in which romance with Hades is only possible in the complete

¹ The TikTok tag #persephone has garnered approximately 847.8 million views, with countless videos responding to the myth on the platform. Such responses are diverse and creative, blending video, music, makeup, cosplay, fanart, and performance, amongst other artistic expressions. See an example here: <https://www.tiktok.com/@milnademilo/video/7319942305438240033?q=persephone%20&t=1705490545895>. All the links in this paper were consulted last on 10/04/2025.

² S. Fogler, 'The Persephone Project', Undergraduate Honours Thesis, State University of New York at New Paltz, 2022, p. 2.

³ A. Hinds, 'Rape or Romance?', *Eidolon*, Jan. 2020, eidolon.pub/rape-or-romance-1b3d584585b8.

⁴ L. Hardwick, *Reception Studies*, Cambridge, 2003.

⁵ Fogler, 'The Persephone Project' (n. 2 above), p. 4. On the not very simple connections between classical mythology and fanfiction, see T. Keen, 'Are Fan Fiction and Mythology Really the Same?', *Transformativ Works and Cultures*, 21, 2016, <https://doi.org/10.3983/twc.2016.0689>.

absence of violence against women, and where young women, as both consumers and producers ('prosumers')⁶ of fanfiction, enjoy life on their own terms and freely celebrate their desires, even whilst societies have yet to make sufficient room for them.

Persephone's Abduction by Hades: The Classical Sources

Before examining the main trends amongst the Persephone fandom, it is important to understand the tradition into which fanfiction is entering, not because fan authors engage directly with specific textual versions of the myth, which they do not, but because they respond directly to the key feature present across all classical sources, offering a radical interpretation of the story. This serves as a valuable first step towards the examination in this and the sections that follow of the creative (and inherently cultural) choices behind modern fan works about Persephone.⁷

The central narrative about Persephone is the so-called myth of the abduction, in which Hades kidnaps her with the intention of marriage.⁸ In ancient Greek and Roman sources, this event is depicted as abrupt and non-consensual: Hades seizes Persephone whilst she is out for a walk, leisurely picking flowers in a meadow alongside several female companions.⁹ The language used by these authors emphasises the brutality of the act and its devastating impact on both Persephone and her mother, who must adapt from their peaceful lives to a new reality dictated by a more powerful (male) god. However, within the context of ancient religion and society, Persephone's abduction was also viewed as a necessary stage in the female life cycle. As a rite of passage, it represented a woman's new social status within the community, her transition from the innocence and protection of girlhood (Kore) to the responsibilities and complexities of adulthood (Persephone).¹⁰ Simultaneously, the story served as a symbolic explanation for alterations in the natural and religious realms. In the *Homeric Hymn to Demeter*, the return of Persephone to the realm of the living coincides with the arrival of spring and the establishment of the Mysteries,¹¹ thus linking her abduction and changes of location to both an account of the earth's annual cycle and the genesis of an ancient cult.¹²

⁶ This concept was introduced by A. Toffler, *The Third Wave*, New York, 1980. For its application to transmedia narratives, see H. Jenkins, *Fans, Bloggers, and Gamers: Exploring Participatory Culture*, New York, 2006.

⁷ Hardwick, *Reception Studies* (n. 4 above), p. 8.

⁸ The allure of Demeter and Persephone in ancient times sparked a multitude of interpretations and literary renditions by classical authors. For scholarly work on the classical sources narrating the myth of Persephone, with extensive bibliography and commentary, as well as for insights into the influence and reception of these texts, see N. J. Richardson, *The Homeric Hymn to Demeter, Introduction, Edition, Translation and Commentary*, Oxford, 1974.

⁹ *Hom. Hym. Dem.* 5.8; *Ov. Fast.* 4.430–56; *Met.* 5.385–95; *Claud. Rapt. Pros.* 2.75–80.

¹⁰ H. P. Foley, *The Homeric Hymn to Demeter: Translation, Commentary, and Interpretive Essays*, Princeton, 1994, p. 81.

¹¹ The Eleusinian Mysteries, held annually in Ancient Greece at Eleusis, were initiation ceremonies in honour of Demeter and Persephone. Despite the secrecy surrounding these rites, scholars generally agree that they likely included the hope or promise of a blessed afterlife, with initiates expected to receive blessings from the two goddesses. See Richardson, *Hymn to Demeter* (n. 8 above).

¹² Foley, *Hymn to Demeter* (n. 10 above), p. 65.

The abduction episode emerged as central to Persephone's story, deemed crucial by ancient Greek and Roman societies on the grounds of the significant information it conveyed. Classical authors showed little interest in delving into other aspects of Persephone's story, particularly her emotions, thoughts, or her rule over the Underworld.¹³ Instead, her tale remained intertwined with the abduction myth and thus the notion of change, whether in relation to women, vegetation, religious rituals, or agricultural practices. The cultural significance of the abduction episode in ancient times might make it surprising that modern readers often overlook it. As demonstrated in this paper, disregarding the abduction is almost standard practice in the Persephone fandom.

Images of Persephone in Mythology-Based Fanfiction

On the fanfiction platform *Archive of Our Own* (hereafter 'AO3') – a fan-owned, fan-run online archive hosting over fourteen million fan works as of April 2024 –, Persephone emerges as one of the most frequently revisited mythological figures.¹⁴ A quick survey of tags (keywords authors use to describe their fanfictions) and summaries written by authors reveals that over half of Persephone fanfictions include tags referencing previous reworkings of the Persephone myth, such as the young adult (YA) webcomic *Lore Olympus* (Rachel Smythe, 2018–2024). The other half starts from either the original myth or other fictional universes, including *Harry Potter* or *Percy Jackson*, which are crossed over with the myth of Persephone.¹⁵

These numbers show that, within these fan communities, some commercially published YA books about Persephone, such as *Lore Olympus*, are more popular than the classical sources of the myth. For many fans, YA books serve as the canon for their Persephone fanfictions. I have previously analysed this phenomenon, usually referred to as 'mediated receptions'.¹⁶ Building on this research, this paper narrows its focus to mythology-based fanfictions for two reasons: first, to explore how fans reinterpret the Hades and Persephone relationship when they engage directly with the key idea of the source myth, namely the abduction by Hades; and second,

¹³ On Persephone's limited role as the wife of Hades and ruler of the Underworld, see C. Salcedo González, 'Perséfone y el Hades: ¿una relación imposible?', in *Violencias políticas contra las mujeres. Imaginarios y espacios*, ed. Rosario López Gregoris et al., Madrid, 2023, pp. 38–52.

¹⁴ As of October 15, 2024, there are 4,192 fanfics featuring Persephone in English, in contrast to 900 for Hercules. See <https://lc.cx/lyITqD>.

¹⁵ For exact numbers and percentages on the different modes of interaction with the Persephone myth on AO3, see C. Salcedo González, 'Mitos clásicos y comunidades virtuales. Perséfone y la fanfiction en español', in *Clasicismo e identidades contemporáneas. La recepción clásica como base de procesos identitarios en el mundo actual*, ed. Luis Unceta Gómez and Cristina Salcedo González, Madrid / Las Palmas de Gran Canaria, 2024, pp. 221–42.

¹⁶ *Ibid.*, p. 230, where I examine how YA fiction 'mediates' the reception of the original story, implanting perdurable themes, such as the consensual bond between Hades and Persephone, or the portrayal of Demeter as an overbearing mother hindering Persephone's access to adulthood. These stories also tend to reinforce traditional gender roles, with Persephone relying on Hades' experience for protection and guidance in matters of love and intimacy.

to provide a more homogeneous dataset, which allows for clearer and more robust findings. This paper's approach raises several key questions that will be considered in my analysis:

1. What does the Hades and Persephone relationship look like when fanfic authors draw directly on the classical sources and are thus familiar with the centrality of the abduction episode?
2. Is the romance trope still common and dominant in these instances? And does this suggest a cross-fertilisation between past and present ideas about the myth, influencing its reception in complex and non-linear ways?
3. How is information from the myth selected and modified to seek new meanings? What (potentially feminist) themes emerge in these mythology-based reinterpretations?
4. What external factors influence these retellings?

Methodology

The analysis begins with a general search on AO3, followed by a quantitative assessment of the results. As of October 15, 2024, an initial search for completed works in English featuring Persephone and Hades as main characters returned 4,192 fanfics. To refine this selection, I applied specific search parameters: crossovers were excluded, and the '(Ancient Greek Religion & Lore)' category was selected under characters and relationships to ensure the resulting fanfictions were based on the classical myth of Persephone. The word count was limited to 1,000–6,000 words, which is the average length of short stories. Furthermore, only fanfics with over 100 likes were included so that the selected works reflected widely accepted ideas within the platform. This process narrowed the selection to 74 fanfics. A review of tags and summaries further refined the list: I discarded duplicates and works that did not directly engage with the myth or did not revolve around Persephone. The final dataset for analysis is 62 fanfics.

The use of Voyant Tools (hereafter 'VT') marks the start of a qualitative evaluation of the fanfics. VT is an open-source, web-based application for reading and interpretation of texts, particularly by scholars in the digital humanities.¹⁷ VT 'was conceived to enhance reading through lightweight text analytics such as word frequency lists, frequency distribution plots, and key words in context displays'.¹⁸ Of the different features it includes, I am primarily interested in the word cloud (a visualisation of top-frequency words), the word frequency lists, and the collocate analysis (word relationships based on how often they appear together). Used together, these tools provide a general and useful view (though limited and superficial) of the fanfics' content and hint at the thematic trends across the 62 fanfics. This serves as a steppingstone for more intensive and focussed readings, to be done later in this

¹⁷ <https://voyant.lincsproject.ca/docs/#/!guide/about>.

¹⁸ L. F. Klein, J. Eisenstein and I. Sun, 'Exploratory Thematic Analysis for Digitized Archival Collections', *Digital Scholarship in the Humanities*, 30.1, 2015, pp. i130–i141.

paper. Fig. 1 presents the word cloud generated by VT for my 62 fanfics after applying the stopword filter.¹⁹

The names *Hades* and *Persephone* are unsurprisingly the biggest words in the cloud. Perhaps a little more surprising (to a non-Persephone fan) is the high frequency in the graph of words like *body*, *fingers*, *mouth*, *hard*, *want*, *bed*, *room*, *wife* and *husband*. This indicates that fans want to write about sexual intimacy. A closer look at the word frequency list (in the Terms panel)²⁰ reveals that the most repeated words can be grouped into three key conceptual areas:

1. Mythological elements: References to central elements of the Persephone myth, such as *Hades*, *Persephone*, and *Underworld*, along with seasonal imagery like *spring* and *flowers*.
2. Physical attributes and bodily states: Words related to body parts (e.g. *eyes*, *hand*, *hair*, *lips*, *fingers*, *skin*), physical states (e.g. *hard*, *warm*, *inside*) and sex (e.g. *pleasure*, *slowly*, *cock*).
3. Emotions and relationships: Terms related to emotional and relational aspects, such as *love*, *want*, *felt*, *thought*, *kiss*, *feel*, and *know*.

These findings suggest that fan authors are primarily drawn to the interpersonal dynamics of the Persephone myth, with a particular focus on the relationship between Persephone and Hades. Rather than on external descriptions, action, or great adventures, these stories' emphasis is on the characters' emotions, personal experiences, and physical affection in private, domestic settings. To further explore how this relationship is depicted, I use the Collocates tool in VT, which identifies words that frequently appear near *Persephone* and *Hades*, revealing their contexts of use and associations of meaning. *Persephone* co-occurs with words like *Hades*, *love*, *Demeter*, and *relationship*, along with references to her physical attributes (e.g. *eyes*, *hand*, *head*, *hair*), epithets (e.g. *queen*, *wife*), and state verbs (e.g. *laughed*, *loves*, *smiles*).²¹ *Hades*, whilst similarly paired with *Persephone*, *Demeter*, *relationship*, and *love*, features more action-oriented verbs like *took* and *groaned*, alongside sexual allusions like *hard*, *inside*, and *cock*.²²

If only tenuously, collocates for *Hades* and *Persephone* hint at a tendency to frame their relationship within conventional gender roles. The most common collocates also suggest a romantic and consensual portrayal of their bond, with moments

¹⁹ This feature makes it possible to remove words, typically non-content bearing words, from the text analysis process.

²⁰ The Terms tab provides a complete list of words in my corpus, ordered by frequency. Both the absolute frequency and relative frequency for each term can be viewed here: <https://voyant-tools.org/?corpus=88703a3f7163914b1fc36dbe5db46171&stopList=key&stopList=keywords-22b69f8c91a551b5996e479f9535f1b9&view=CorpusTerms>.

²¹ See here the complete list of collocates for *Persephone* <https://voyant-tools.org/?corpus=88703a3f7163914b1fc36dbe5db46171&lang=en&stopList=key&stopList=keywords-22b69f8c91a551b5996e479f9535f1b9&query=persephone&view=CorpusCollocates>.

²² See here the complete list of collocates for *Hades* <https://voyant-tools.org/?corpus=88703a3f7163914b1fc36dbe5db46171&lang=en&stopList=key&stopList=keywords-22b69f8c91a551b5996e479f9535f1b9&query=hades&view=CorpusCollocates>.

of joyful interaction, as evident in words like *laugh*, *kiss*, *love*, and *smile*. Sexual intimacy between Hades and Persephone is also a recurring theme. Leveraging the whiteList feature to focus on specific words of my choice, namely *I want*, *content*, *love*, *happy*, *pleasure*, *love Hades*, *love Persephone*, *hate*, *rape*, *abduction*, *trauma*, further shows the prevalence of the romantic reading of the myth.²³ References to rape, abduction or Persephone's suffering are less prominent and even rare (Fig. 2).

Whilst VT is valuable for an initial exploration of a large corpus, its qualitative findings are ultimately insufficient. The insights it provides are superficial and inconclusive, often misleading. For instance, VT suggests that because the fanfictions depict Persephone and Hades as a traditional heterosexual couple adhering to fixed gender roles, the readings of Persephone on AO3 are necessarily conventional and conservative. Yet, VT falls short in detecting subversive elements in these portrayals due to its inability to provide a deeper qualitative analysis. A closer reading of the corpus shows that romanticized interpretations can indeed be politically and socially conscious and serve as a form of feminist resistance and subversion.

Trends in Persephone Fanfiction

Reading the 62 fanfictions about Persephone on AO3 allowed me to qualify the findings provided by VT and take them further. These fan readings can be classified into two broad groups:

1. Texts **erasing rape** and only including romance ('only romance' trend): 43 texts, roughly **70%**.
2. Texts **mentioning rape**: 19 texts, approximately **30%**, further divided into:
 - Texts that mention rape but rehabilitate/justify Hades' actions ('rape and romance' trend): Approximately **20%**.
 - Texts that denounce violence and exclude romance entirely ('only rape' trend): Approximately **10%**.

The preference for the omission of the abduction episode stems from the belief that the premise of rape eliminates the possibility of a romantic relationship between Hades and Persephone. When rape is mentioned in these fanfics, there are two possibilities: about 10% exclude romance altogether, in line with the perspective that rape is incompatible with romance. Meanwhile, the remaining 20% attempt to reconcile rape with love, but, as they can't accept rape as it is depicted in the classical sources, they often include an apology from Hades, an acknowledgement of his actions, a transformation on Hades' part, or a problematic justification of his behaviour.

To illustrate these trends, I have selected a few representative fanfics based on their popularity on AO3 (as reflected by kudos,²⁴ shares, and comments). This

²³ The whiteList feature operates like the stopword filter but in reverse: it restricts word cloud visualisations to display only the selected words, rather than excluding them and displaying all others.

²⁴ Kudos are a one-click form of positive feedback, similar to 'likes' on social media platforms.

ensures that the examples that are examined reflect widely embraced interpretations of Persephone on the platform.

a. 'Only romance'

Texts within the 'only romance' trend make no reference to Hades abducting Persephone or taking her against her will, focussing instead on detailing their intimate and domestic interactions within the context of their relationship. Since these narratives hinge on the idea that non-aggression towards women is a pre-requisite for romance, they often place Persephone in the role of rectifying the notion that Hades abducted her. In the fanfiction 'She would swallow the world' by spacediino, Persephone confronts her mother to clarify the truth and defend her life with Hades: 'You think my bed is cold. You think my husband stole me from you. You are wrong. He saw in me the hunger which you cannot see, and he offered himself'.²⁵ In addition to these corrections, a recurring feature is Persephone's sincere and sometimes exaggerated expressions of love for Hades, as seen in 'Worship' by genericfanatic, where she refers to him as 'the absolute best in the world, and the underworld and Olympus'.²⁶

For many fans, stressing Persephone's agency within Hades' realm is a key concern. In 'Persephone, My Queen', it is Persephone who proposes marriage: 'After eating the pomegranates, "I want a wedding", she chimed, the flutter in her chest beaming out of her in a smile – a genuine thing that hid no scheme'.²⁷ She also dictates the terms of their union, asserting, 'I want to be a bride and dress like one. I want flowers here, lots of them, to wear in my hair and around my ankles. [...] And have you swear yourself to me, sacred oath and all'. Her self-assuredness and unapologetic femininity indicate her refusal to conform to traditional expectations of female submission within a relationship.

The fact that these texts write out the abduction by Hades does not mean a disregard for the themes of abuse and consent central to the myth. On the contrary, many address these issues, suggesting that Persephone's explicit consent is an important condition for any romantic connection in the present. This is exemplified in katy-faise's 'A turn of winter', which portrays Persephone's bond with Hades as one rooted in empathy and mutual care, as shown when, before intimacy, Hades ensures that Persephone is comfortable and explicitly seeks her consent: "Is this alright?" he asks, and she nods'.²⁸

By including such moments, these fanfictions encourage readers to reconsider elements of the classical sources that were once unimportant and irrelevant. In ancient Greece, a woman's agency in expressing her needs was not typically a priority, and people of that time saw Persephone's emotions differently compared to how modern readers view them. Fanfiction authors, however, insert modern ideas of women's autonomy in sex and romance into the ancient myth. With their fanfics, and

²⁵ <https://rb.gy/9q4noe>.

²⁶ <https://rb.gy/yakigf>.

²⁷ <https://rb.gy/6qmtew>.

²⁸ <https://rb.gy/sqp7qg>.

Fig. 2 Word cloud for the whiteList feature. (Source: <https://voyant-tools.org/tool/Cirrus/?stopList=&whiteList=keywords-c071d8fb555ca69e0e9260e78e23b387&visible=25&corpus=88703a3f7163914b1fc36dbe5db46171>).

had found herself imagining his fingers on her skin—pressing fingers into bruises and teeth against taut nipples’. When these desires are realized, she fully embraces her pleasure, prioritizing her own satisfaction over Hades’. This focus on Persephone’s sexual agency is further emphasised in ‘I’ve Missed You, My Queen’, where she often initiates intimacy and voices her desires with confidence. In one instance, she asks Hades, ‘Put your fingers inside me’, to which he eagerly replies, ‘Yes, My Queen’, indicating that he consents and is willing to please her. The story continues with candid and joyful descriptions of their physical closeness, where Persephone teaches Hades to do things a certain way to ensure her satisfaction. This and other fanfictions put Persephone’s desires highest on the priority list, presenting a fantasy world where women say what they want openly, instruct their partners when necessary, and embrace and seek their pleasure without reservation, whilst their partners respond with kindness, self-awareness, and a willingness to meet their needs.

b. ‘Rape and romance’

A small percentage of authors on the platform (20%) fall into the ‘rape and romance’ trend. In these fanfictions, Hades abducts Persephone for different reasons, ranging from divine fate, his isolation in the Underworld, or a personal vendetta against Zeus. The issue with this approach is that it attempts to reconcile Hades’ past rape of Persephone with the development of a romantic relationship between them in the present. This is arguably the most problematic reinterpretation of the Persephone myth, one that has rightly faced criticism from scholars and readers alike.

Within this group, the most troubling examples (and the least numerous) present an uncritical romanticisation of rape without depicting a reformed Hades; in other words, he neither alters his behaviour nor explicitly apologizes to Persephone. Instead, Persephone comes to understand his motives and ultimately excuses his actions. This is the case of ‘Seeds of Love’ by stefanie_bean, which has Persephone narrate how Hades ‘dragged’ her down in a manner that reminisces classical accounts of the abduction episode.³⁰ Very quickly we come to realize that this

³⁰ <https://rb.gy/00mdbg>.

fanfiction does not have Persephone – or young women – in mind in passages like the following: ‘you took me on a vast bed of obsidian carved into the shape of a swan, laid with black silk sheets. The long hot length and breadth of you pounded my virginity to shreds until at last I lay crying and helpless. You covered me tenderly and wiped the tears that I’d missed, and then you were gone’. Such a description, couched in sensual imagery, feels implausible as the voice of a victim, and demonstrates a startling insensitivity.

As the story progresses, the initial act of violence – already romanticized in its depiction – gives way to romantic feelings, as Persephone transitions from fear to acceptance and eventual affection for Hades. The underlying implication that love can arise from violence risks normalizing the idea that a relationship can develop positively after an abusive start without the abuser taking responsibility or making reparations for his actions. Crucially, this text does not target the trauma Persephone would experience and hence sidesteps the ethical and emotional repercussions of Hades’ behaviour. By avoiding any meaningful engagement with these consequences, the text reduces Persephone’s experience to a sexually suggestive plot device.

Within the ‘romance and rape’ trend, the previous approach that depicts a love story without ‘reforming’ Hades is less common. More often, Hades is portrayed as a transformed man: he either apologizes to Persephone openly or shows signs of changed conduct and regret. A paradigmatic example is ‘Post tenebras, spero lucem’ by AceQueenKing. In this fanfiction, Persephone views Hades’ action as a violation of her agency, evident in her thoughts of him as a ‘strange ruler who promised love but had kidnapped her without a single word’.³¹ The key element here is that Hades acknowledges his error in disregarding Persephone’s wishes and expresses remorse for the way he initiated their relationship. His apology is paired with an admission of ignorance about courtship norms. Furthermore, Hades reflects on the violent traditions of marriage amongst gods, distancing himself from his father and brothers who ‘wedded’ their wives through coercion or deception. Hades implies that, unlike the dominant male figures in his family, he wishes to build a different type of relationship.

Hades asks Persephone for a fresh start, explicitly seeking her consent with a hesitant ‘Would you like to go for a walk with me?’. His desire to earn her trust and hear her ‘yes’ sets him apart as a male figure aware of his power yet unwilling to misuse it. However, by the story’s end, Persephone justifies Hades’ actions, reflecting that he might be ‘so desperately lonely’ and admitting she ‘almost’ understands his motives for abducting her. This transition to forgiveness and devoted love for Hades, framed as her seeing his perspective, excuses Hades’ violation and trivializes its severe consequences. Once more, it seems as though the kidnapping was employed here not as a horrific event but rather a plot device (albeit not a justifiable one) meant to foster romance, and within a form, style and genre of writing specifically aimed at sexual arousal through violence.

³¹ <https://rb.gy/89xthk>.

Even when Hades apologizes, changes, or shows awareness of the impact of his actions on Persephone, these texts often run the risk of minimizing the severity of the abduction and its consequences. This is because fanfiction authors tend to favour the themes of love, passion, emotional intensity, and satisfying, happy endings. This inclination in fanfiction is fundamentally at odds with maintaining a critical outlook in exploring the aftermath of abuse or sexual violence. In my view, attempting to reconcile Hades' abduction of Persephone with the development of a genuine bond results in fanfictions that lack credibility and sensitivity in addressing these themes.

Ultimately, whilst the fanfictions discussed in this paper are largely shaped by a desire to create safe, feminine, and accessible content for personal enjoyment – often in contrast to the representations offered by mainstream entertainment industries – it is also necessary to recognize the presence of more extreme and explicit forms of erotic content within the genre, as exemplified by the 'rape and romance' trend. Even within spaces defined by a preference for 'only romance', some texts explore hardcore (and sometimes unethical) scenarios involving violence or BDSM. These examples reveal that fanfiction engages with a wide range of erotic practices and, at times, explores the complex and controversial intersection between rape fantasies, consent, and romantic resolution.

c. 'Only rape'

On AO3, approximately 10% of fanfictions reference Hades' abduction to denounce its lasting physical and psychological effects on Persephone. In AceQueenKing's 'Longing, Bright and Haunting', Hades is remorseful and repeatedly apologizes for having 'taken her under the earth, taken her flowers, [...] taken her life [...] stolen her; his stomach twisted in guilt'.³² His pleas for forgiveness are met with Persephone's silence. She never expresses love for Hades, nor does she forgive him. The story ends with Hades' self-assuring reflection: 'They had eternity, after all, measured in three-month increments'. Like in the classical sources, the Persephone in this fan story must return to the Underworld each year, a prospect Hades views with visible contentment. This reflection by Hades amplifies Persephone's grim reality – a life trapped in hell, a cyclical return to her captor, even though she is unhappy and does not want to engage with him in any way. The ending is impactful as it shines a spotlight on the consequences of Hades' actions for Persephone. By framing these consequences through Hades' perspective, this fanfic emphasises that remorse and a desire to change are insufficient to undo the harm caused. Hades' apologies do not change her unwanted fate.

AceQueenKing furthers into Persephone's psychological pain in 'water full of salt'. Persephone's memories of the event are fragmented – 'a broken flash, illuminated only by lighting-hot pain pricks upon her'³³ – reflecting the dissociative manner in which trauma is often experienced. In the Underworld, Persephone feels utterly abandoned, and wishes for 'someone to pray to who was not her mother, who

³² <https://rb.gy/3ftmnj>.

³³ <https://rb.gy/v6irx9>.

cannot hear her nor help her here in a realm without life'. Even the divine earth mother Demeter is powerless in the Underworld. Hades exacerbates this isolation with his refusal to acknowledge the harm he has inflicted. He minimises his actions as unfortunate circumstances beyond his control rather than his choices. His manipulative tone is evident as he patronizingly claims, "You will learn to appreciate what I offer", he murmurs, the tone seductive. A lie. She will not. She will never'. Despite her vulnerable state, Persephone sees through his deceit and even rebuffs Hades' attempts to give her a new name and sever her bond with Demeter: "It's Persephone", she says, crisply. "Persephone, daughter of Demeter". In this retelling, Persephone has a feminist and humanist vocation as she denounces a broader system of violence against women who are treated as mere pawns in the games of powerful men.

Feminist Potential in Romance Readings of the Persephone Myth

It is crucial to note that fanfictions inscribing romance into a narrative that begins with abduction constitute a minority (20%) within the broader reception of the myth online. For most fans of the Persephone myth on AO3 (80%), violence against women is fundamentally incompatible with pleasure or romantic attachments. This raises important questions for this paper: What drives the proliferation of these romanticized readings, and what factors are shaping their interpretations? Can these readings ever be understood as feminist?

Feminist scholar Aimee Hinds Scott argues that omitting or disregarding rape in contemporary mythological retellings 'is, at best, irresponsible, as it perpetuates harmful tropes and can result in real-world harm'. In addressing romantic readings of Persephone, she comments:

Although Persephone's abduction might have been unproblematic in ancient Greece, to tell it as a romance today erases the experiences of both ancient and modern women. [...] When artists do not address the problematic themes like sexual abuse in the myths they use, they potentially do lasting damage as their own work becomes part of the corpus on that particular myth. These issues have real world consequences, reinforcing rape culture.³⁴

Scholars have also noted that rewriting Persephone's marriage to Hades as a choice she willingly makes and finds beneficial is complicit with patriarchal and heterosexual norms.³⁵ Whilst I agree that the romantic formula can, in some cases, reinforce certain sexual and gender power dynamics and stereotypes, I also argue that this is not *all* they are doing.

Unlike her largely missing presence and limited voice in the classical sources, the fanfictions examined here focus our attention firmly on Persephone's experience and

³⁴ Hinds, 'Rape or Romance?' (n. 3 above).

³⁵ Fogler, 'The Persephone Project' (n. 2 above), p. 57. Persephone fandom mainly features heterosexual couples: 51 out of the 62 fanfics I analyse fall into this category.

make her the exclusive or primary speaker. Insofar as these texts elevate Persephone to the role of principal narrator-focalizer, we may feel tempted to label them as ‘feminist’ rehabilitations of the classical Persephone. However, Lillian Doherty cautions against equating female voices and privileged female characters with female agency and power.³⁶ The subjectivities of Odyssean women and goddesses such as Penelope and Arete are the very definition of a ‘siren song’ in Doherty’s terms, a female voice that conceals the text’s androcentric, patriarchal, and aristocratic underpinnings, hence invoking a sympathetic female audience. ‘Siren songs’ disappoint on closer inspection; even if they have women speak profusely, ‘siren songs’ are not feminist songs because of the values they ultimately reinforce.

From this it follows that whilst Persephone may speak eloquently and memorably in fanfiction, play significant roles in the plot, and receive admiration or respect from Hades or other characters, this does not necessarily signify female autonomy or empowerment. Building on Doherty’s proposal, Rachel Lesser similarly suggests that feminist retellings require more than a female voice:

‘it matters whom or what a woman speaks about. [...] It matters for what purpose she speaks – her agenda. It matters whom she speaks to. It matters how her speech is answered [...] whether her speech coincides with effective action – her degree of agency’.³⁷

Drawing on Doherty’s premise and Lesser’s criteria, I argue that the ‘only romance’ fanfictions about Persephone achieve most of these goals, which qualifies them as ‘feminist’ retellings.³⁸

Regarding whom or what Persephone speaks about, in most examples, she discusses issues of sex and love in her relationship with Hades, which is portrayed as a model of healthy and fulfilling physical closeness, in stark contrast to the brutality and coercion of the original text. These fanfictions counteract the violence inherent in the original myth by turning the traditional story on its head, transforming it into an unexpected source of pleasure and satisfaction for women. Rejecting the traffic in stories predicated on sexual and gendered violence constitutes a form of narrative

³⁶ L. E. Doherty, *Siren Songs: Gender, Audiences, and Narrators in the Odyssey*, Ann Arbor, 1995, pp. 9–16. Doherty asserts that contemporary adaptations of classical myths inevitably reflect the gender norms and practices of our own cultural context. She mentions the portrayal of Hades and Persephone falling in love as an example of this. See L. E. Doherty, *Gender and the Interpretation of Classical Myth*, London, 2015, p. 23.

³⁷ R. H. Lesser, ‘Ancient and Modern Voices of Briseis: a Feminist Critique’, *Classical Receptions Journal*, claf002, 2025, <https://doi.org/10.1093/crj/claf002>. In a seminal work for Gender Studies, Alicia Ostriker argued that contemporary women authors engage in a process of ‘revisionist mythmaking’ as an act of both imaginative and political necessity. She also identified specific techniques employed by women in their revisions, such as reversing traditional plots, giving voice to previously silenced female figures, reshaping myths to foreground female experience, exposing the gendered biases entrenched in the original myths, and using irony, parody and recontextualization. See A. Ostriker, ‘The Thieves of Language: Women Poets and Revisionist Mythmaking’, *Signs*, 8.1, 1982, pp. 68–90.

³⁸ This argument is supported and enriched by Radway’s analysis of popular literature, Fogler’s exploration of Persephone in fanfiction, and Popova and Döring’s valuable perspectives on gender and sexuality from a Fan Studies lens.

resistance, not the least because some examples also resist conventional notions of female modesty in sex. In the examples explored, Persephone is in control of her sexuality and ensures that her experiences are pleasurable primarily for herself. This is seen in the moments when she expresses what she wants unapologetically and plainly.

Fanfiction readings about Persephone have elicited mixed reactions, all of them very passionate. The internal conflicts of feminism are reflected in Persephone fanfiction, which is influenced by these discussions and participates in them. The #MeToo movement, which has pushed survivors to speak out against sexual violence and frequently uses ancient examples as symbols of feminist resistance, makes the reactions both inside and outside of fan culture particularly understandable. However, because fanfiction's content depends on the features of its medium of expression, it cannot be evaluated against the standards of traditional literature or activist feminism.

Fanfiction is conceptualized as a safe space for experimentation or for writers to voice ideas that are not acceptable (and are deemed taboo) in published fiction.³⁹ Their 'eternal' work-in-progress quality⁴⁰ prevents us from asserting that the readings presented in fanfiction are final or fixed. The fanfiction community lends itself to imaginative escapism, folly, literary experimentation, and playful interaction.⁴¹ Engaging with fan spaces for academic analysis thus demands both a high degree of non-judgement and an awareness that these works are created within a distinct context and for purposes that diverge from those of conventional and commercial literature.⁴² These factors regarding genre shape the reception of Persephone online and explain the form(s) she takes in fan culture.

Who Persephone speaks to in these 'only romance' fanfictions is also telling of their subversive possibilities. Persephone often speaks about (her relationship with) Hades but not necessarily to him. Building on the widely accepted notion within Fan Studies that fanfiction is predominantly produced by and for women, LGBTIQ+ individuals, and young people,⁴³ it follows that the Persephone fandom likely consists of young women and/or queer people writing for others like themselves within this community. Through the figure of Persephone – another young female – fan authors directly voice their own passions and desires and, by extension, their own community's desires, particularly other young women, who are both readers and contributors ('prosumers') to the fandom. This creates an intimate, peer-to-peer appeal, where young women write directly for each other about things they deem crucial, such as enjoying sex with your partner. In telling each other what they want, fan authors are reaffirming those desires through storytelling, convincing themselves

³⁹ Döring, 'Erotic Fan Fiction' (n. 29 above), p. 4. See the discussion above concerning fans' depictions of extreme sexual practices designed to elicit arousal through violence.

⁴⁰ Kristina Busse and Karen Hellekson, 'Introduction: Work in Progress', in *Fan Fiction and Fan Communities in the Age of the Internet: New Essays*, ed. Karen Hellekson and Kristina Busse, Jefferson, 2006, pp. 5–32 (6–7).

⁴¹ Fogler, 'The Persephone Project' (n. 2 above), p. 65.

⁴² *Ibid.*, p. 6.

⁴³ Döring, 'Erotic Fan Fiction' (n. 29 above), p. 2.

in writing that what they desire is legitimate and that they are deserving of it. The conversational and community-based nature of fanfiction lends itself to using it in this way.

The latter aligns with the purpose of these fanfictions: to craft a fantasy where happiness for young women is attainable. In this fantasy, Hades seeks Persephone's consent (as in 'A turn of winter'), Persephone teaches Hades how to do things that are enjoyable for her (as in 'I've Missed You, My Queen'), and she is not portrayed as the victim of violence but the agent of her own pleasure. Fanfiction, serving as a way for communities to process their everyday experiences, especially regarding gender and sexuality,⁴⁴ crystallises what its authors and readers lack in their own lives and truly hope for. Reading these 'only romance' texts, one gains a clear idea of what they want: to enjoy life fully, embrace intense emotions, especially love and desire, to feel enamoured, loved, and desired, enjoy physicality without fear or shame, and live unapologetically and openly.

This female fantasy, which expands and is projected across different texts with variations, provides authors and readers in the Persephone fandom with the certainty that real life often denies them. In her reference work on female readers and romance novels, Cultural Studies scholar Janice Radway notes women have turned to romance before and now out of a very real 'dissatisfaction, longing, and protest',⁴⁵ in search of a 'utopian' aspiration. Similarly, Persephone fanfiction is spearheaded by a 'utopian' impulse to imagine relationships that are more equal and pleasurable for their creators. Against the backdrop of a reality where sex remains unpleasant, dangerous, or painful for many (young) women,⁴⁶ these retellings reimagine Persephone not as a victim crying for her mother's rescue but as a sexually forward young woman crying for pleasure.

When Persephone's speech prompts Hades to act in ways that realize her desires, these fanfictions demonstrate the kind of female agency that Lesser identifies as central to feminist storytelling. The focus is not on Hades' approval, but on Persephone's ability to effect change through her voice and will. Beyond the effect of Persephone's speeches within these stories, it is worth noting their effect outside the texts. The 'only romance' reading has become the dominant interpretation in fan culture,⁴⁷ crystallizing into 'fanon' – a fan-created pop culture canon that displaces the ideas established by classical sources. Fanon is 'a fantasy based on the needs

⁴⁴ M. Popova, "*Slight Dub-Con but They Both Wanted it Hardcore*": *Erotic Fanfiction as a Form of Cultural Activism around Sexual Consent*, PhD dissertation, University of the West of England, 2018, p. 50. Despite the anonymity of the Internet, the likely age and gender of fanfiction 'prosumers' is going to make them more attuned to the issues of love, intimacy, sexuality and gender.

⁴⁵ See J. A. Radway, *Reading the Romance: Women, Patriarchy, and Popular Literature*, Chappel Hill and London, 1991, p. 215.

⁴⁶ N. J. Roberts, 'Gender, Sexual Danger and the Everyday Management of Risks: The Social Control of Young Females', *Journal of Gender-Based Violence*, 3.1, 2019, pp. 29–43 (29–33).

⁴⁷ This is confirmed by my searches on AO3, where 70% of the fanfictions interpret rape as romance, as well as by other scholars examining the myth of Persephone in fandom; see Fogler, 'The Persephone Project' (n. 2 above), p. 2.

of individual writers rather than the reality established by shared source text'.⁴⁸ Grounded in fantasy and wishful thinking,⁴⁹ fanfictions about Persephone reflect the longings and needs of young women. Those aspirations have contributed to creating a female and feminist fanon that reimagines Persephone's story by writing out the abduction episode and pulling romance into the 'official story.'

Writing and reading fanfiction is often debased as the concern of 'crazy fangirls',⁵⁰ a label that downplays the cultural significance of fan work. Nevertheless, there is an element of subversion to have stories produced by the so-called 'crazy fangirls' enter mainstream culture. The romanticized reading, which thrives in the 'marginalized' genre of fanfiction⁵¹ and is attentive to young women's desires, has found its way into more canonical spaces, such as television. A paradigmatic example is the 2024 Netflix TV series *Kaos*, which cannot be suspected of being produced by 'crazy fangirls' and has indeed been lauded in intellectual (and predominantly male) circles for its comedic and sharp reimagining of classical myths. In episode eight of *Kaos*, Persephone echoes the 'only romance' reading when she confronts Hera about the Olympians' fabrication of her abduction: 'Every kid on Earth, when they learn about the Underworld, they think I'm there against my will. They pity me. They think I was kidnapped, raped, in some cases. And a pomegranate. I don't eat pomegranate. I am allergic. They think I don't love Hades. [...] I love Hades for real'.⁵²

Fanfiction reclaims 'lesser' forms, such as the romance mode, which focuses on the interior and domestic rather than external adventures or grand epics. This reclamation is also subversive, as it gives prominence to literary approaches, themes, and motifs traditionally overlooked or undervalued by academic disciplines.⁵³ The success of the 'only romance' readings in being implanted into more mainstream cultural spaces underscores their disruptive potential. This is yet another example of Persephone's speeches resonating beyond the confines of fanfiction.

Ultimately, the 'only romance' fanfictions have feminist motivations because they provide Persephone with varying degrees of intellectual, personal, and sexual autonomy, thereby contributing to a progressive understanding of (young) women's roles

⁴⁸ C. Driscoll, 'One True Pairing: The Romance of Pornography and the Pornography of Romance', in *Fan Fiction and Fan Communities in the Age of the Internet: New Essays*, ed. Karen Hellekson and Kristina Busse, Jefferson, 2006, pp. 79–96.

⁴⁹ *Ibid.*, pp. 79, 88.

⁵⁰ Fogler, 'The Persephone Project' (n. 2 above), p. 62. On social perceptions of canon and fanon, see R. Liebler and K. Chaney, 'Canon vs. Fanon: Folksonomies of Fan Culture', *MIT Media in Transition*, 5, 2007, pp. 1–16.

⁵¹ The shift in portraying Persephone and Hades' relationship as a love story is also evident in contemporary YA fiction such as Rachel Smythe's *Lore Olympus*. Fogler, 'The Persephone Project' (n. 2 above), p. 25 argues that, despite the popularity and influence of works like *Lore Olympus* in today's fanfiction, key ideas in the Persephone fandom (especially Persephone and Hades' love story) predate YA fiction. Beyond the issue of who said it first, I think that YA fiction influences and is influenced by the Persephone fandom. Their shared themes, and the fact they are both 'lesser' and popular productions, create a reciprocal relationship, with novels drawing fans to the fandom and vice versa.

⁵² Episode 8, 06:30–07:17. C. Covell (Creator), *Kaos* [TV series], Netflix, 2024.

⁵³ Radway, *Reading the Romance* (n. 45 above), p. 212.

in romantic relationships. This is not to say that texts recasting rape as romance are always progressive with regards to the portrayal of gender norms.⁵⁴ Persephone in these stories mainly speaks about Hades and her world is limited to her experiences with him. In addition, whilst she is aware of some issues related to gender norms, Persephone attains what she yearns for because she is in a privileged position, unrestrained by social class, race, or any other form of exclusion.⁵⁵ Overall, fanfiction may be imperfect in its feminism, but that does not mean it cannot achieve, as demonstrated in this paper, some feminist objectives.

Conclusions

My preliminary findings were methodological: the characteristics of fanfiction (its large corpus, dynamism, interactivity, playful nature, and work-in-progress quality) necessitate the use of a variety of methods to understand the phenomenon. A combination of quantitative and qualitative approaches, such as the use of Voyant Tools and close reading, has allowed for a more nuanced understanding of these texts and their contexts. VT has been helpful in finding recurring themes in depictions of Persephone, including her love for Hades and the depiction of their relationship as harmonious and fulfilling. Close readings have corroborated these findings and offered deeper observations into the beliefs of the Persephone fandom. Most importantly, they have shown that fans draw nuanced images of Persephone, combining the elements they are familiar with, foregrounding ‘only romance’, ‘rape and romance’, or ‘only rape’ in their stories as they see fit. Using concepts from different disciplines, among them Classical Reception, Gender Studies, and Fan Studies, has helped account for the diversity of factors (literary, cultural and ideological), shaping romanticized perceptions of the story.

The ‘only romance’ readings, analysed through the feminist criteria proposed by Lesser, reveal that the female voice in Persephone fanfiction does challenge gender norms to some extent. This is evident in what she speaks about, who she addresses, the purposes of her speech, and its effects both within and beyond fan culture. Whilst these fanfictions may not always challenge the gender binary or subvert all patriarchal beliefs, they carve out a space for female and feminist fantasies to be expressed, practised, legitimized, and blatantly rebutted. The romanticized retellings in fanfiction also mirror contemporary debates within feminism, particularly in how they resonate with the contested issues of female pleasure, autonomy, and consent. In this way, these fanfictions engage with broader cultural and ideological concerns, illustrating how fan communities – often marginalized or dismissed as ‘feminine’,

⁵⁴ Some fans paint a more traditional portrait of Hades’ and Persephone’s roles in the context of their romance. In ‘The Persephone Effect’ by UntouchedElegance, the goddess is a compassionate and nurturing figure, tasked with saving Hades from his ‘unruly’ and cold nature with her empathy and love. <https://rb.gy/weobyb>.

⁵⁵ For an insightful commentary on these aspects of Persephone fanfiction, see Fogler, ‘The Persephone Project’ (n. 2 above), esp. 65–71.

‘crazy’, ‘nerdy’, or ‘frivolous’ – can enact forms of feminist resistance, even when those forms appear reductive, impractical, or imperfect.

Overall, this paper has highlighted the dual role of digital tools, both as an object of study, the central element in the creation and dissemination of fanfictions, and as a methodological instrument for indexing and analyzing that corpus. This intersection foregrounds the digital not only as a subject of inquiry but also as an integral part of the research process in the field of Classical Reception.

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